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FUNDAMENTALS OF MIGRATION SOURCE STUDIES OF THE UZBEK USSR (BASED ON ARCHIVAL MATERIALS OF UZBEKISTAN)

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Nowadays the world community is experiencing difficult and global migration processes in a legal and illegal manner. This issue related to the migration of the population is an urgent problem in modern Uzbekistan. The purpose of this study is to historically identify the main stages of industrial development and the formation of migration processes in construction and industrial zones, as well as the solution of the personnel issue on the example of Bukhara region.

Research methods. In this work uses source studies, chronological sequence, content analysis, survey method and comparative analysis, for an accurate study of this issue

Results and discussions. The article describes the study of the migration issue, swinging 1950-1980. The article also mentions unused materials that remained far from the human eye, in which all reliable information about the state of industrial migrants on the territory of the Uzbek SSR is hidden. Also shown are the resolutions in which the strict control of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR could not change the everyday situation of worker migrants. Also noted are materials proving peaceful life with the local population in multinational regions such as Gazli, Karaul-Bazar, Kagan, Zarafshan.

Conclusion. Some facts related to the policy of industrial migration and its implementation with the help of state support from an economic and material point of views are derived and based on the data of the Central Archive of Uzbekistan and the State Archive of Bukhara region.

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Introduction: A comprehensive study of the migration issue allows you to accurately and in-depth imagine the difficulties and difficulties of the development of the industrial and construction process, passed by the people of the Uzbek Republic after the Second World War. To display the role of the resolutions of the Central Committee of the KPSS and the Ministries in the reform of industrial zones on the ground, in the formation and change of a developed fishing society on the territory of Uzbekistan, was of great importance for the history of the country. This difficult path was a test, first of all, for states that did not expect a global change in the field of industrial development in 1950-1980, one of these states was the Uzbek SSR, in which industrial centers were built in such areas as Bukhara, Tashkent, Fergana, Karshi etc.

In this regard, the source study of research in the study of industrial migration and classifications of labor personnel plays a large role in the history of Migration in the Soviet Union. The study of the history of the migration policy of the Soviet Union in the history of the Uzbek SSR was based mainly on sources and formal documents from the RSFSR (Russia) and the Eastern part of the European North. In certain cases, it played the role of resolutions of the Central Committee of the KPSS in which they did not pay attention to the implementation of these laws within the regional departments, in which we will carefully study issues related to the implementation of resolutions in the republican and regional order.

Materials and methods. to determine the degree of study of sources and historiographical materials on population migration in the post-Soviet state methods were used; source studies, oral history, comparative analysis. Methods of historiography, content analysis and methods of using information articles were used to study the reasons for the migration of workers in industrial zones in the archives of the Bukhara region.

Results and discussions. The main archival materials of the Central Republican Archive of Uzbekistan, the state archive of Bukhara region and districts became the basis of the source base for studying research. Many of these documents were disclosed by us in a scientific study for the first time, and put into scientific use. It should be noted that in the studied archival materials, first of all, the documents of the central archive of Uzbekistan, accumulated in some funds, stand out. These are documents of funds, P-837 fund, op. 1 “Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR”, which contains all decrees and resolutions written personally by the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR according to the resolutions of the Central Committee of the KPSS and the Councils of Ministers of the USSR. Such decrees and resolutions were preceded by one written on behalf of the chairman of the Central Committee of the KPSS and submitted to the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR about a particular problem and its solutions.

R-2347 fund "Main Directorate of Resettlement under the Council of Ministers of the USSR Uzbekistan" - this fund contains all archival documents related to the population census and their socio-economic data in which, after examining this data, they decided who and where to relocate (mostly it was done from densely populated area to sparsely populated lands for irrigation of new virgin lands). There were also information about able-bodied and qualified people for migration to industrial zones and their statistics.

R-2765 fund, op. 1 “State Committee of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR on the use of

labor resources” - these materials contain minutes of meetings, accounting reports on the use of labor resources and reports on the work carried out in the implementation of the plans, correspondence with the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan and the State Committee of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR on the use of labor resources.

P-2348 fund, op. 1 “The Main Directorate of the Organized Recruitment of Workers and Employment under the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR” - this fund contains documents covering the mechanisms for adopting economic resolutions, in particular the Resolutions of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR and the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan on issues of further development of the industrial economy and information on the course of implementation of the decisions.

Basically, these are plans for an organized recruitment of all fishing institutions throughout the republic, which separately noted all the work done by organizational recruitments and regional executive committees in the entire history of 1950-1980, in relation to providing labor resources for all governing bodies of industrial and construction organizations in which, according to decrees Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR and the Central Committee of the KPSS were sent to the so-called work to ensure the development of industrial Uzbekistan. And this is also a source of reports, reports, summaries and certificates on the execution of decisions of the Main Migration Directorate under the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR for all the years of the history of migration processes in the USSR. Most of these materials were practically not studied before the research of this work. But it is precisely these studies that make it possible to explain the whole situation in which the government was entrusted at different social and economic levels, in the relationship between the leadership and the people. The best part of these materials is the saturation of details that characterize the whole environment of the working forces in the industrial zones of the country.

For example, by order of the Ministry of Labor Reserves of the USSR from the head of the main department of organized recruitment of the USSR M. Polyakov, in which, according to the decree of May 7, 1952 No. which clearly ordered to submit to the approval of the councils of ministers of the republics on the distribution of an additional plan for the recruitment of workers in the second and fourth quarters of 1952, to the aid of the Ministry of Construction of Heavy Industry Enterprises at the expense of the plan. The orders were put forward to the heads of the main departments of vocational railway schools and schools F30 of the Ukrainian SSR Pogrebny, the heads of the republican departments to the Ministries of Labor Reserves of the Kazakh and Uzbek SSR Karibaev and Yunusov¹, in general, the issue of migration of an additional labor force in the amount of 1700 people was resolved. The second example could be an order to send additional labor to the undeveloped energy sector of the Uzbek SSR, in which, in addition, about 6081 people were required to migrate for 1952-1955². Such materials contain a variety of information about the migration policy and the activities of the industrial structure of the Uzbek SSR, including in the Bukhara region³. Particularly worthy are materials relating to the period of construction of residential buildings, during the migration of industry for workers. Since in such a situation, the postponement of questions about the state of conditions for labor workers led to an activity of staff

¹ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 17, Case – 14, SH20.

² Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2347, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 71, Case – 16, SH43

³ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2765, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 15, Case – 3, SH48. // Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 837, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 2, Case – 11, SH52.

turnover, in which there was a surge in the social situation of a shortage of workers in the regions of the Uzbek SSR and in the industrial zones of the Bukhara region, which had great potential to provide all the necessary conditions⁴.

With the beginning of the reconstruction of the industrial policy of the USSR after the Second World War, it was necessary to transfer all industrial zones from the western part of the country (European) to the eastern part and place some in the countries of Central Asia, which, in turn, were not criminal in relation to hostilities and had a huge labor resource, which made it possible to provide all areas of construction and industry with the necessary strength for further development⁵. This structure was intended to include all the Ministries of Construction and Industry of the USSR in the fishing policy⁶. The first years of the 50-60s refer to the migration of workers for the development of industrial zones in Siberia, the Urals, the Kazakh SSR, the Caucasus - the city of Konstantinovka, the Stalin Region, the city of Ust-Kamenogorsk, the city of Zyryanovsk, etc⁷.

These documents have a high degree of authenticity, are emotional and rich in a large number of details reported by the Regional Executive Committees, departments of organized recruitment and campaign affairs commissars, who were direct eyewitnesses of the events. However, sometimes they convey the views of stakeholders and are not always objective in assessing the current situation.

For example, the information obtained on the fund R-2348 "Management of Organized Recruitment of Workers and Employment under the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR", there are some provisions about the lack of workers for additional sending to industrial zones that have not been fulfilled by this plan of 1956⁸. Or the resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR and the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan, which notes that the pace of industrial construction and the size of the workers being commissioned do not meet the increased needs of the republic⁹. Interesting is the situation in which the state of the industrial enterprises themselves, which were in great demand in the labor force, is not noted, the question is also raised what kind of labor force did they need? The exact answer lies in the next document of the Central Archives, which became the most important for the topic under study, was the document of the fund R-837 "Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR" in a letter dated No. sending skilled workers¹⁰, which the Uzbek SSR so badly needed.

In these funds, cases related to foreign migrants on the territory of Uzbekistan, letters and protocols of local regional executive committees to police departments, materials of perusal of letters from unorganized workers were put aside. In this fund R-2348 there are materials of the departments of the organizational recruitment of Bukhara, Samarkand and Kashkadarya on the movement of the population

⁴ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 34, SH117. // Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 71, Case – 17, SH60. // Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 44, SH173

⁵ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 34, SH161

⁶ Министерства и Тресты - Промышленность строй материалов, предприятия металлургии и химической промышленности, Трест «свинецстрой», строительство СССР, промышленность энергостанции «Гидроэнергострой», предприятия нефтяной промышленности, предприятия Угольной промышленности, строительства автотранспорта и шоссейных дорог, лесная промышленность, Транспортное строительства, Строительства городских и сельских домов.

⁷ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 17, SH64.

⁸ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 17, SH44.

⁹ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 34, SH29.

¹⁰ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 837, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 20, SH64.

of the 1950s¹¹.

Of particular attention and value are the protocols of cluster meetings of employees of the departments of the organized recruitment of workers of the Samarkand, Bukhara and Kashka-Darya regional executive committees, in which the deputy head of the department I.N. Knyshev, the inspector of the department K.M. Ivanov were present, from the Sredhydroenergostroy trust, head of the personnel department I.I. Kobzev and deputy head of Khishraugestroy Zakirov, and head of the personnel department Samartsov. From the Bukhara head of the department R. Nurullaev, workers comrades Sabirov, Shaimanov, Zychkov. They resolved the issues of the reason for the lack of qualified personnel in the industrial and construction zones of qualified personnel in the Uzbek SSR¹². The activities of the workers are considered in these documents in connection with the lack of national staffing in the Bukhara region. The protocols and letters contained in this case shed light on some little-known details of the population of the Uzbek people. The people who received a ticket by the organizational recruitment to stay in industrial zones throughout the USSR. For example, there is an extensive regulation regarding the collection by regional departments of organized recruitment among students and former military personnel in the Bukhara region in favor of industrial zones. These materials will allow us to trace a number of specific facts on the history of industrial migration.

At that time, the settlers mainly carried out their labor contracts through an individual contract with enterprises. Basically, such employment contracts were drawn up with local workers who had their own personal home and life, and for enterprises such an environment was beneficial, the reason was not the creation of additional living conditions for them¹³. These funds are also saturated with documents containing specific information, facts and names¹⁴.

Materials from the Archive of the Bukhara Region also became an important source. Documents from the Fund 1172 - "The Bukhara Organized Recruitment of Workers, the Republican Organized Recruitment Office"¹⁵ - mainly orders and protocols for the Republican Organized Recruitment Office in the Bukhara region. Decisions of the Executive Committee of the Bukhara Regional Council of Working People's Deputies for 1952-1965.

Fund - 1234 "Bukharagaspromstroy"¹⁶ - this fund stores protocols, reports and agreements of the collective office on construction management, on the conclusion and implementation of contracts, on labor protection and safety of workers, checking the structure of living conditions and housing and communal apartments for labor workers.

Fund - 1219¹⁷ "Oil and gas production department "Bukharaneftegaz(Bukhara oil and gas)" of the Economic Council of the Uzbek SSR" - these documents contain information about the title lists of survey and design work, resolutions and orders of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR on the capital construction of residential buildings and objects "Bukharaneftegaz".

¹¹ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 35, SH95.

¹² Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 35, SH1.

¹³ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 44, SH12.

¹⁴ Центральный Архив Узбекистана F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN . – 5, Case – 35-44-57-64, SH1-191.

¹⁵ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1172, Inventory – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 15-16-32.

¹⁶ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1234, INVENTORY. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 296, Sh.236.

¹⁷ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1219, INVENTORY. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 29-42-82-102-148.

Fund - 1023¹⁸ "Executive Committee of the Bukhara Regional Council of Workers' Deputies" - this fund is divided into 2 types of the level of documents that are stored in the archive (special and identical). Here we used the decisions and execution of the work done by the executive committee of the Bukhara region on migration issues in industrial and construction zones.

Fund – 946¹⁹ "Department of Statistics of the Bukhara Region" provide an opportunity to familiarize yourself with orders, decisions of executive committees, materials (certificates, acts, memorandums) on checking the condition of industrial workers, annual statistical reports on the number and composition of the education of workers and specialists of industrial enterprises, which are the primary source to the study of industrial progress and the migration of specialists in the development of this case. They contain valuable indications of the course of industrial migration, the decisions and execution of local governments, statistical assessments of the dynamics of the population in the region and the personal qualities of individual workers who have shown themselves from the best and the worst. These materials reflect the conclusions of the Ministries on the implementation of the republic and its regions, and will significantly supplement the shortcomings of materials from the Central Archives of Uzbekistan. The most important source is the official documents regulating organized recruitment plans. This type of document includes drawing up plans on the one hand and execution on the other.²⁰ The documents are executed by explanatory notes on the main activity of the Bukharaneftegaz oilfield department, which provides all assistance in fulfilling the production plan and providing all the workers sent by the organizational recruitment of the department of the Bukhara Regional Executive Committee, reports on the creation of all living conditions for migrants of this industrial prognosis²¹. This decree on the implementation of the plan for organizing the recruitment of highly skilled workers throughout the region, was put forward a plan for campaigning work called "experience of the best" which was the practical development in the industry.

The fact is a letter drawn up from the deputy head of the Uzbek Republican Department of the Ministry of Labor of the Reserves of the USSR Kalanov to the regionally authorized organization of the recruitment of workers of the Bukhara region Nurullaev, which spoke of sending a brochure entitled "experience of the best", it was proposed to work out this brochure among the employees of the office and enterprises about improving the working capacity among workers Trudoviks, practical measures were sent to the republican office.²² Such materials make it possible to see and substantiate all the additions to the shortcomings of the industrial provision of workers. This also includes contracts concluded by individual workers and the Department of Organizational Recruitment for the lead industry, in which the State had more extensive conditions for labor workers. In the general state of affairs, since as a rule the lead industry was located in cities and workers' settlements, the enterprises had clubs, libraries, hospitals, ten-year schools, kindergartens, shops, and canteens. Dormitories were provided for single workers, and separate rooms for families.²³

¹⁸ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1023, INVENTORY. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 998-2023-110-1061-1273-1325-1388-1262-215-944.

¹⁹ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 946, INVENTORY. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 1552-1314-1487-1513.

²⁰ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1172, INVENTORY. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 32, SH135

²¹ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1219, INVENTORY. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 82, SH66

²² State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1172, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 15, SH453.

²³ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1172, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 15, SH375.

The main reason for migrating to the industrial zones was the guaranteed experience and the acquisition of secondary and higher educational diplomas because, starting from 1952-1973, each industrial zone had to have a highly skilled worker in order to successfully develop experience.²⁴ Sources of the same type include legal acts of workers and their disciplines that have been adopted since the beginning of 1950²⁵.

These documents regulate the attitude of the people to the policy of the state and determine the status of all industrial enterprises in terms of working conditions, the demand for doing work and household guarantees, with the help of labor contracts made individually and by an organized recruitment department. It was they who played an important role in the development of industrial and construction progress in relation to the Bukhara region, since, according to statistical data, the Bukhara region was a donor for the development of the entire oil and gas industry and the provision of workers throughout the Republic in which there were not enough specialists²⁶. Thus, these documents are very important sources covering the history of migration relations that influenced the development of events in the Bukhara industrial region.

As a source of interest is also a collection of letters sent to the Deputy Manager of the Trust Buharagazpromstroy on Bulgarian issues Marinov I.Ya, about the situation of the Bulgarian citizens²⁷ detained for burglary. This little-known material was compiled on the basis of archival data from the cities of Zarafshan, Navaiy, Gazli, pos. the town of Karavulbazar and the districts of Peshku, Shafirkan, Vabkent and Gijduvan. It was in these cities and regions that the Bulgarian workers who arrived under the 1969²⁸ agreement between the countries of the USSR and the BNSR were located. According to the same archival data, on the territory of the construction zone SU-1 pos. Gazli also had and worked workers from other nations such as Russians, Jews, Germans from the GDR, Poles, Ukrainians, Tatars, Kazakhs and of course, in very small numbers, Uzbeks. I want to remind you that all these highly qualified specialists arrived at trust Buharagazpromstroy for one reason, and this was the lack of engineers and highly educated specialists in the field of gas production in the Bukhara region.²⁹ Judging by these documents, it can be assumed that the government seriously considered the number and impact on the development of industry of qualified and highly educated specialists working in all industrial zones of the Bukhara region.

But there is also the possibility of distrust of specialists, from local residents who, in turn, were highly qualified and also did not have special documents on graduating from technical schools and institutes, the reason was the provision of work for all students who did not finish secondary schools, which, in turn, studied special 4-6 monthly courses to improve skills in the enterprises themselves³⁰.

As a comparative source material, the official publication of statistics from the archives was used, the Ministry of Statistics for eight years from 1972-1980, 139,500 workers arrived in all industrial towns of the Bukhara region, who in turn were from all union republics, in addition they were relocated to industrial

²⁴ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1172, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 32, SH3.

²⁵ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1234, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 296, SH1.

²⁶ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1219, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 42, SH120.

²⁷ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1234, INVENTORY. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 314, SH146

²⁸ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1234, INVENTORY. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 296, SH26.

²⁹ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1219, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 148, SH2.

³⁰ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1172, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 32, SH69.

and construction areas to improve the productivity levels of skilled workers.³¹ Such a publication certainly has its contribution to mixing traditions and creating new relationships among all nations in the Bukhara region.

For an objective and comprehensive analysis of the industrial migration of states, materials from the Bukhara State Archive, unknown to our national history, are also extremely important. We used documents from some funds, in which personal letters were kept about the requests of all the workers of the settlement of the town of Karaulbazaar of the Kagan region³². Also, the funds store almost all the documents of industrial enterprises that have survived to the present from the moment of its foundation until the formation of an independent republic. The funds of the state archive deposited a wide range of sources covering the history of the development of the industrial period and with a high degree of reliability. These documents make it possible in many respects to assess the situation and significantly supplement with facts a number of aspects of industrial construction enterprises and their connection with the planned and organized recruitment department.

In the first years of industrial development, significant changes began to occur due to the implementation of reforms, many government institutions were reorganized. For example, the organized recruitment of workers since its founding in 1945, the beginning of reforms in the management system and responsibilities regarding issues of recruitment of workers, privileges and division of departments from the organizational recruitment itself to the planning department³³.

For example, in 1949 - the Main Resettlement Administration under the Council of Ministers of the USSR, 1950-1952. - the departments of supply and re-evacuation were abolished, 1953 - division of the departments of resettlement into, southern and eastern territories (management was transferred to the Ministry of Agriculture), 1956 - the structure of organized recruitment under the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR was divided into five departments, 1957 - organizational recruitment was changed to the Department of Organized Recruitment of Workers and Employment under the Bukhara Regional Executive Committee³⁴, 1960 - Main Directorate for Resettlement and Organized Recruitment of Workers, 1966 - State Labor Committee, 1976 - State Committee of the Council of Ministers of the USSR on Labor and Social Affairs, 1980 - in Goskomtruda created a department for organizing resettlement for work and a department for monitoring the preparation of farms for the reception of migrants.³⁵ Thus, from the beginning of the first years of industrial development in the Uzbek SSR, not only the industrial zones themselves were reorganized and conditions were created to provide labor for the entire population of the country. In this regard, it became necessary to examine all the archives that existed at that time. It turned out that the archives are in excellent condition.

Thus, in order to develop the industrial environment and improve the everyday life of industrial and construction workers, documents were found in the archives of the Bukhara region confirming the poor preparation of industrial towns and settlement towns for the acceptance of workers, of course, for such global activities on the acceptance and creation of conditions for labor workers in which control was not possible. For example, in terms of the construction of residential buildings for migrant workers in the

³¹ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 946, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 1552, SH61.

³² State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1219, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 148, SH90.

³³ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1023, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 998, SH55.

³⁴ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1172, Inventory. – 2, ST.UN – 1, Case – 14, SH10.

³⁵ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1234, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 314, SH52.

Bukhara region, it was in a very disastrous state, since in 1956, in terms of preparing residential buildings in the amount of 7,500 for 1957, only 18%³⁶ were completed throughout the republic. At the same time, such construction in the Bukhara region was not started in 1957. Such indicators, of course, indicate the reliability of the materials of the Bukhara archive.

The lack of manpower in industry is also mentioned in a 1958 document in the Bukhara region to Yusupov, the regional representative of the organizational recruitment of workers in the Bukhara region, that from January 1 to June 1, 1958, the district inspector Fayziev systematically underfulfills the tasks set for her from month to month and thereby underdoes the country's industry, the planned number of workers, was supposed to send 100 workers to the country's industry, but actually sent 61 people³⁷. systematic non-fulfillment of the labor plan was not the fault of the departments themselves. Archival research proves that the lack of numbers was due to a lack of highly skilled workers, and not to a lack of unemployed people themselves.

First of all, the data used from the fund 1219 contained all the correspondence of officials who came to Bukharaneftegaz with the help of an organized recruitment of workers, contracts, orders, data of workers who arrived with their families. Reports on the implementation of the capital construction plan of the association "Bukharaneftegaz" found lists of persons who received residential buildings under the contract, 4 years after the start of the individual contract³⁸.

Most of the documents have the following compositional design: the documents provide a symbolic doxology for the good of the Soviet government. This is followed by the name of the ministry or department where the document was sent. Then came the text of the letter and at the beginning the registration and number were also indicated, after the text of the main part there was a signature confirming who sent the letter or order.

The research and study of archival materials was not limited to central and regional archival materials; the bulk of the time was also devoted to studying materials from regional archives. The materials of the district archive of the city of Zarafshan, which to this day is an industrial town of the Navai region, the then part of the Bukhara region, were studied in the chronology of the study of our work.

Fund 2 - "The Executive Committee of the Zarafshan City Council of Workers' Deputies. General Department" - this fund contains documents on the decision of the regional council of deputies and materials on improving the work of industrial bodies for the workers of an industrial city³⁹.

Fund 7 - "Murantou Council of Working People's Deputies" - these archives contain the activities of the Zarafshan Council of Deputies on the further development and placement of productive forces in the cities of Zarafshan, Murantou, Uchkuduk, etc⁴⁰.

Fund 17 - "Tamdy and Altyntau settlement council" - in the materials of this case, the lists of deputies and their execution according to the decisions of the regional council of the Bukhara region are well preserved. Unlike other industrial towns, Zarafshan was distinguished by its local industrial enterprises, for example, according to the decree of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan and the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR dated December 24, 1975 No. factories in the

³⁶ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1023, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 998, SH223.

³⁷ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1172, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 15, SH454.

³⁸ State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1219, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 381, SH68.

³⁹ District Archive of the City of Zarafshan F – 2, Inventory. – 1, Case – 2-18-20-34-35-42-48-49.

⁴⁰ District Archive of the City of Zarafshan F – 7, Inventory. – 1, Case – 4-5-8-22-24-26-29-55-28-46-66-91-94.

village of Uchkuduk, a car service station for 6 posts in the city of Zarafshan and a specialized enterprise for the repair of complex household appliances⁴¹.

The materials of the districts of Shafirkan, Gijduvan, Ramitan, Peshku, Vobkent and Zhandar archives were also studied. Which were stored in funds 4 "Executive Committee, Ramitan District Council of Workers' Deputies" (Peshku), Fund 5 - "Executive Committee, Sverdlovsk District Council of Workers' Deputies" (Jondor), fund 22 - "Executive Committee, Kagan District Council of Workers' Deputies" (Kagan), fund 2 - "Executive Committee, Karmana District Council of Workers' Deputies" (Navoi region), Fund 115 - "Executive Committee, Alat District Council of Workers' Deputies" (Alat), fund 1 - "Executive Committee, Shafirkan District Council of Workers' Deputies" (Shafirkan), Fund 3 - "Executive Committee, Gijduvan District Council of Working People's Deputies" (Gijduvan), Fund 6 - "Executive Committee, Karavulbazar District Council of Working People's Deputies" (Kagan).

These documents are considered the most important sources for this work, because these materials are considered to be the donors of completed cases on the history of industrial migration in the Bukhara region. The selectively used materials of the district archives are a factor in the work done on the construction and organization of all able-bodied workers and the creation of all conditions by industrial enterprises for migrants in these industrial construction zones.

As the most important material, there were also lists of all citizens living in the working settlement of Gazli, in which income tax was calculated with the population for 1962-1970. and a list of those who arbitrarily began perestroika to improve their everyday lives and exempt them from income tax⁴². There are also reports "on the transfer of pasture land for permanent use of the K. Rovat state farm to the Dzhaneldy state farm⁴³" and the establishment of a boundary for the allotment of pastures for the construction of the Bukhara Ural Gas Pipeline. Thus, thanks to these lists, we were able to clarify the exact demographic data of the Ghazli settlement and its outskirts. Protocols and Decisions on the withdrawal of land plots from land users of the collective farms of the region and their transfer to the directorate of the Bukhara-Ural gas pipeline under construction in the amount of 20.0 hectares, of which 10.50 hectares are permanently used for the construction of the Bukhara-Ural gas pipeline and the Amu-Darya-Gazli⁴⁴ water pipeline.

Conclusion: In the course of analyzing the problems of this topic, the relevant sections of the work made conclusions that related to certain issues such as: the creation of huge industrial production capacities, the development of industry took place under the growing influence of scientific and technological development. Under the conditions of the socialist economic system, changes in the sources of replenishment are due to socio-economic factors, such as the migration of peoples to industrial zones, which included the improvement of the structure of industrial production and the training of qualified personnel. Also, the living conditions of workers in the areas of industrial and construction enterprises.

References:

1. Central Archive of Uzbekistan F – 2348, Inventory - 1, ST.UN. – 17, Case – 14, SH.20.
2. Central Archive of Uzbekistan F – 2347, Inventory - 1, ST.UN. – 71, Case – 16, SH.43

⁴¹ District Archive of the City of Zarafshan F – 7, Inventory. – 1, Case – 4, SH45.

⁴² District Archive Peshku F – 4, Inventory. – 1, Case – 180, SH158.

⁴³ District Archive Peshku F – 4, Inventory. – 1, Case – 61, SH123.

⁴⁴ District Archive Jondor F – 5, Inventory. – 1, Case – 380, SH157.

3. Central Archive of Uzbekistan F – 2765, Inventory - 1, ST.UN. – 15, Case – 3, SH.48.
4. Central Archive of Uzbekistan F – 837, Inventory - 1, ST.UN. – 2, Case – 11, SH.52.
5. State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1234, INVENTORY. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 296, SH.236.
6. State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1219, INVENTORY. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 29-42-82-102-148.
7. State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1172, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 15, SH.453
8. State Archive of Bukhara region F – 946, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 1552, SH.61.
9. State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1023, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 998, SH.55.
10. State Archive of Bukhara region F – 1234, Inventory. – 1, ST.UN – 1, Case – 314, SH.52.
11. District archive Peshku F – 4, Inventory. – 1, Case – 180, SH.158.
12. District archive Jondor F – 5, Inventory. – 1, Case – 380, SH.157.
13. District Archive of Zarafshan City F – 7, Inventory. – 1, Case – 4, SH.45